

33°0'0"E

34°0'0"E

35°0'0"E

36°0'0"E

37°0'0"E

Hellenistic sites in Plain Cilicia (Turkey)

SRTM data: CGIAR-CSI v4.1

sites: database „Siedlungskammer Kilikien v1“
based on published survey and excavation data

hydrological data: generated manually and by
using the function flow accumulation (ArcGIS v9)

by Susanne Rutishauser

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.2591665

38°0'0"N

38°0'0"N

37°0'0"N

37°0'0"N

36°0'0"N

36°0'0"N

projection: UTM Zone 36N
datum: WGS 1984

• sites dating to the Hellenistic Period